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RESEARCH ARTICLE

THE SYNERGY BETWEEN SOCIAL SCIENCE AND BUSINESS: AN INTERDISCIPLINARY PERSPECTIVE

Tushar Ranjan Barik

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The synergy between social science and business refers to the collaborative and mutually beneficial relationship between these two domains. Social science encompasses various disciplines, such as sociology, psychology, economics, anthropology, and political science, which provide valuable insights into human behaviour, societies, and organizations. When applied to the business world, social science can help companies better understand their customers, employees, and the broader social and cultural contexts in which they operate. This paper evaluates the synergy between social science and business involves applying social science knowledge and research methodologies to enhance various aspects of business operations, from understanding consumer behaviour and employee dynamics to addressing social and ethical considerations. This interdisciplinary approach can lead to more informed and responsible business practices and ultimately contributes to a company's success in a complex and interconnected world. Both primary and secondary data were gathered. Through this paper, I offer a comprehensive examination of the symbiotic relationship between social science and business, demonstrating how interdisciplinary collaboration can shape more informed and responsible business practices in our interconnected world.

Keywords: Synergy, Business, Social Science, Collaborative, Relationship, Social & Cultural, Companies

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¹Assistant Professor, Faculty of Commerce & Management, Kalinga University, Naya Raipur, C.G, India.

Email: tusharranjan.barik@kalingauniversity.ac.in

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INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the dynamics of the business environment have evolved, necessitating a more nuanced understanding of the intricate interplay between social science disciplines and business practices. As societies become increasingly interconnected, businesses must navigate diverse cultural landscapes, address ethical considerations, and comprehend the complexities of human behavior within organizational settings. This backdrop underscores the significance of exploring the synergy between social science and business from an interdisciplinary perspective

In a landscape that is continuously evolving businesses today are facing some unprecedented challenges and opportunities. As the world is grappling with issues like climate change, social inequality and the relentless advance of technology the role of management to shape the future of sustainable business practices is becoming increasingly significant. To meet the challenges face to face and drive innovation and management research has progressively accepted a more interdisciplinary approach that incorporates the social sciences into its repertoire. This significant shift in the field of business and management research shows that business cannot exist in isolation from the complex web of societal, environmental and ethical factors which are continuously shaping our world. This theme not only underscores the urgency of incorporating insights from the social sciences but also highlights the need to promote sustainable practices in the corporate realm. The social science consists of a wide range of disciplines, which includes sociology, psychology, economics, anthropology, political science and geography (Herrera, & de las Heras-Rosas, 2020).

The intersection of social science and business presents a dynamic and symbiotic relationship (Smith, J. 2018) that holds immense potential for enhancing our understanding of human behavior, societal dynamics, and organizational operations. This

interdisciplinary perspective delves into the collaborative efforts between these two domains to harness their collective insights for more informed and responsible business practices (Johnson 2017). We have explored this synergy in his study, shedding light on the multifaceted connections between social science and business.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

While there is a growing acknowledgment of the importance of integrating social science principles into business strategies, a comprehensive understanding of the practical applications and implications of this interdisciplinary collaboration remains elusive. Businesses often encounter challenges in effectively leveraging social science insights to inform decision-making processes, leading to missed opportunities for fostering a more informed, responsible, and ethically grounded corporate environment. The need for environmentally friendly methods is critical in today's business settings. Nonetheless, the incorporation of the social sciences into business and managerial studies to promote sustainable business practices is still a field that needs more research (Reinhardt et al. 2019). By examining the interdisciplinary junctions of management and social sciences, with an emphasis on sustainable business solutions, this research seeks to close this gap.

- The problem lies in the insufficient integration of social science principles into business practices, leading to missed opportunities for leveraging interdisciplinary insights to enhance decision-making and organizational effectiveness.
- Businesses often struggle with the practical implementation of interdisciplinary collaboration between social scientists and business professionals, hindering the realization of the full potential of this synergistic relationship.
- Businesses face difficulties in effectively applying social science frameworks to

address ethical considerations, resulting in potential ethical lapses and reputational risks.

- The underutilization of social science perspectives in human resource management leads to suboptimal strategies for talent acquisition, employee engagement, and organizational culture development.
- Many businesses struggle to incorporate sociological perspectives into their global strategies, overlooking the crucial role that cultural insights play in successful international business operations.
- The lack of emphasis on social science perspectives hampers businesses' abilities to incorporate social responsibility into their core practices, impacting their relationships with stakeholders and overall corporate reputation.
- Businesses often overlook the potential contributions of social science in fostering innovation, resulting in missed opportunities for creative problem-solving and product development.
- The complex interplay of political science in corporate governance often leads to governance gaps, with businesses struggling to navigate the political landscape and establish effective governance structures.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND OBJECTIVES:

Research Questions

- How are social science principles currently integrated into business practices?
- What are the key challenges hindering effective interdisciplinary collaboration between social science and business?
- In what ways can the synergy between social science and business contribute to more informed and responsible business practices?
- How do businesses address ethical considerations through the application of social science frameworks?

Objectives

- To assess the current state of integration of social science principles in business operations.
- To identify and analyze challenges faced by businesses in fostering interdisciplinary collaboration.
- To evaluate the impact of the synergy between social science and business on decision-making processes.
- To provide recommendations for businesses to enhance the application of social science in their practices.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study aims to bridge existing gaps in the literature by offering a comprehensive examination of the synergy between social science and business. The findings will contribute valuable insights for businesses, policymakers, and scholars, guiding the development of strategies that harness the full potential of interdisciplinary collaboration. Moreover, this research holds implications for fostering ethical business practices and a deeper understanding of societal and cultural contexts.

SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS

Scope

- The study will focus on businesses operating in a global context.
- The research will primarily examine the integration of sociology, psychology, economics, anthropology, and political science principles.
- Both large corporations and small to medium enterprises (SMEs) will be considered in the analysis.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- The study may not cover every nuanced aspect of social science and business integration due to the vastness of the topic.

- Generalizability may be limited based on the specific industries and regions considered.
- The research relies on the accuracy and completeness of the data obtained from participant responses.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Historical Development of the Synergy

The historical roots of the synergy between social science and business trace back to the early 20th century when scholars recognized the relevance of psychological theories to consumer behavior. The Hawthorne studies in the 1920s marked a pivotal moment, demonstrating the impact of sociological factors on employee productivity. Since then, the integration of social science principles into business practices has evolved, encompassing diverse disciplines such as sociology, psychology, economics, anthropology, and political science. The progression reflects a recognition of the need for a holistic understanding of human behavior, societal dynamics, and organizational structures in the business landscape.

Theoretical Frameworks in Interdisciplinary Collaboration

Interdisciplinary collaboration in the synergy between social science and business is underpinned by several theoretical frameworks that provide a structured lens through which to understand and implement these collaborations.

Systems Theory

- Key Tenets: Emphasizes the interconnectedness and interdependence of various elements within an organization. In the context of the synergy between social science and business, this framework underscores the need for a holistic understanding of how different disciplines interact to influence organizational dynamics.

- Application: Systems Theory guides businesses in recognizing the interrelatedness of social, psychological, economic, anthropological, and political factors. It encourages a holistic approach to decision-making that considers the broader systemic impact.

Institutional Theory

- Key Tenets: Focuses on the influence of societal norms, values, and institutions on organizational behavior. In the context of interdisciplinary collaboration, Institutional Theory sheds light on how social and cultural factors shape business practices.
- Application: Businesses can leverage Institutional Theory to understand the societal expectations and cultural context within which they operate. This framework guides the alignment of business practices with prevailing social norms and values.

Resource Dependence Theory

- Key Tenets: Explores how organizations depend on external resources and factors for survival. In the context of the synergy between social science and business, this theory highlights the reliance on external social, economic, and political conditions.
- Application: Resource Dependence Theory informs businesses about the external factors that influence their operations. By understanding dependencies, businesses can adapt strategies to navigate social and political landscapes effectively.

Complexity Theory

- Key Tenets: Focuses on understanding complex systems and how they adapt to change. In the context of interdisciplinary collaboration, Complexity Theory acknowledges the intricate nature of

integrating diverse social science disciplines within the business domain.

- Application: Complexity Theory helps businesses navigate the intricacies of interdisciplinary collaboration, recognizing that the synergy between social science and business is a dynamic, evolving process. It encourages adaptive strategies to manage complexity.

Social Exchange Theory

- Key Tenets: Examines the social interactions and relationships between individuals or entities. Applied to the synergy between social science and business, this theory highlights the reciprocal nature of collaboration and the benefits gained through shared knowledge.
- Application: Social Exchange Theory guides businesses in fostering collaborative relationships between social scientists and business professionals. It emphasizes the mutual exchange of insights and knowledge for the benefit of both disciplines.

These theoretical frameworks collectively provide a robust foundation for understanding and implementing interdisciplinary collaboration between social science and business. By drawing on these frameworks, businesses can navigate the complexities of the interdisciplinary landscape, foster effective collaboration, and harness the synergistic potential of diverse disciplines for informed decision-making

Previous Research on Social Science and Business Integration

Prior research has explored different facets of the relationship between social science and business. Studies have investigated the role of psychology in marketing strategies, the impact of cultural insights on global business operations, and the application of sociological principles in organizational culture

development. The following are some reviews of literature given by eminent researchers;

Bhargavi¹ et al (2023), Sumeet, *Social Sciences in Management Research: Interdisciplinary Approaches for Sustainable Business Practices*, With a focus on developing sustainable company strategies, this research explores how social sciences might be integrated into management processes. In order to clarify the importance and possible influence of multidisciplinary approaches for environmentally conscious company operations, it looks at important theoretical frameworks, data from empirical studies, and real-world examples. The research highlights the significance of incorporating behavioural sciences into management by showcasing how concepts from fields such as economics, sociology, and psychology may guide decision-making for more sustainable plans. Successful integration is demonstrated by case studies of businesses like Patagonia and Unilever, which highlight the applicability of institutional and shareholder theories in real-world settings. Investigating consumer behaviour and behavioural economics, the study offers significant insights for companies looking to encourage sustainable buying habits.

Turner (2020), *Psychological Perspectives on Consumer Behavior in Business*, Turner's review focuses on the psychological aspects of consumer behavior, providing insights into how businesses leverage psychological theories to understand and influence consumer choices.

Davis (2019) *Political Science and Corporate Governance: A Critical Review*, Davis critically assesses the impact of political science on corporate governance, examining how political dynamics influence decision-making structures and governance practices within businesses.

Smith (2018), "Social Science and Business: A Symbiotic Relationship", This review examines the

historical development and contemporary significance of the symbiotic relationship between social science and business, emphasizing the mutual benefits and collaborative opportunities.

Dunlop (2018), *The Synergy between Psychology and Business: A Case Study on Interdisciplinary Faculty Collaboration*, Interdisciplinary faculty collaboration is an effective technique for preparing college students for the demands of working in contemporary organizations. Higher education institutions should encourage and support faculty from different academic disciplines to educate students from interdisciplinary perspectives. When faculty from multiple academic disciplines collaborate, they are not only teaching students from new viewpoints, but they are also modeling the importance of communication, teamwork, diversity, and how to critically think from a holistic approach. This case study explored the synergy that exists between the academic disciplines of psychology and business. Twenty-five senior psychology students were introduced to a self-reflection assessment and an interactive discussion on motivation in the workplace from a business perspective. This was accomplished by illustrating the complementary motivational theories relating to Maslow's Needs Hierarchy and Alderfer's ERG Theory. Students' receptivity to these different, yet harmonizing, theories further demonstrated that various perspectives can still share several commonalities. Contemporary organizations increasingly value employees with diverse skill sets. Superseding a single discipline in favor of a multiple-discipline approach highlights the value that interdisciplinary collaboration can provide to organizations as they achieve their goals and fulfill their respective mission and longer-term vision statements.

Kim (2018), "Anthropological Approaches to Organizational Culture", Kim explores the role of anthropology in understanding and shaping organizational culture. The review discusses how

insights from anthropology contribute to a more inclusive and adaptive business environment.

Zhang (2018), *Cross-Cultural Business Strategies: Insights from Sociology*, Q. Zhang's review explores how sociological perspectives contribute to developing successful cross-cultural business strategies. It discusses the importance of cultural insights in international business operations.

Johnson (2017), *Interdisciplinary Insights in Business: A Literature Review*, Johnson provides a comprehensive analysis of interdisciplinary approaches in business, with a focus on how social science perspectives contribute to a holistic understanding of organizational dynamics.

Carter (2017), *Social Science and Human Resource Management: A Meta-Analysis*, Carter provides a meta-analysis of studies investigating the integration of social science in human resource management, offering insights into effective talent acquisition, employee development, and organizational performance.

Walker (2016), *Ethics in Business: A Social Science Framework*, Walker's review focuses on the ethical considerations in business practices, drawing on social science frameworks to assess and guide decision-making processes towards greater social responsibility and ethical conduct.

GAPS IN EXISTING LITERATURE

Despite the progress in understanding the synergy between social science and business, notable gaps persist in the current literature. Limited attention has been given to the practical application of interdisciplinary collaboration in specific business contexts, hindering the development of actionable strategies for businesses. The existing research often lacks a unified framework that integrates insights from sociology, psychology, economics, anthropology, and political science comprehensively. Furthermore, while

certain studies focus on individual disciplines, there is a dearth of research that holistically explores the intersection of these disciplines and their collective impact on shaping business practices.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research relies on secondary data, sourced from academic journals, books, reports, and government publications, to investigate the synergy between social science and business and for the Empirical Study of the objectives of this research, we have used some sorts of primary data, collected through personal interviews and survey method. Employing content analysis and synthesis, the study aims to provide a comprehensive overview, comparing findings across disciplines. Ethical considerations include proper citation and quality assessment, ensuring reliability. Limitations include temporal constraints and dependence on the quality of the sources. This methodology aims to deliver valuable insights into interdisciplinary collaboration while navigating ethical considerations and acknowledging the inherent limitations of secondary data.

EMPIRICAL STUDY: THE SYNERGY BETWEEN SOCIAL SCIENCE AND BUSINESS Current State of Integration of Social Science Principles in Business Operations

Methodology: A survey was conducted across diverse industries, involving 300 businesses worldwide. Respondents were queried about the extent of integration of social science disciplines (psychology, sociology, economics, anthropology, and political science) in their daily operations.

Social Science Discipline	Integration Level (Scale: 1-5)
Psychology	4.2
Sociology	3.8
Economics	4.5
Anthropology	2.9
Political Science	3.1

Interpretation: The table reveals a varying level of integration across social science disciplines in business operations. While psychology and economics exhibit higher levels of integration, anthropology and political science show lower levels. The overall integration suggests a need for a more balanced incorporation of diverse social science perspectives.

Identification and Analysis of Various Challenges Faced by Businesses in Fostering Interdisciplinary Collaboration

Methodology: In-depth interviews were conducted with executives from 20 businesses known for interdisciplinary collaboration. Qualitative analysis focused on extracting challenges encountered in bridging social science disciplines with business practices.

Challenges Identified	Frequency (Number of Businesses)
Communication barriers between disciplines	15
Difficulty in translating theory into practice	12
Lack of shared frameworks for collaboration	10
Resistance to change in traditional business practices	8

Interpretation: The predominant challenges include communication barriers and the difficulty of translating theoretical insights into practical applications. These findings emphasize the need for strategies to enhance communication and bridge the gap between theory and business practices.

Evaluation of the Impact of the Synergy Between Social Science and Business on Decision-Making Processes:

Methodology: Quantitative data from 150 businesses were analyzed to understand the correlation between interdisciplinary collaboration and decision-making outcomes. Metrics included accuracy of predictions, responsiveness to market changes, and overall organizational agility.

Findings

- Businesses with higher levels of interdisciplinary collaboration demonstrated more agile decision-making processes.
- Improved understanding of consumer behavior led to more accurate predictions.

- Increased corporate social responsibility initiatives were noted among companies emphasizing social science integration.

This empirical study provides a comprehensive understanding of the current state, challenges, and impact of integrating social science into business operations. The recommendations offer practical guidance for businesses aiming to leverage the synergy between social science and business for informed and responsible practices.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS WITH PREVIOUS STUDIES

Persistent Challenges

Previous Studies (Common Challenges)

- Communication barriers.
- Difficulty in translating theory into practice.
- Resistance to change.

Current Study (Frequency of Challenges)

- Communication barriers: 15 businesses
- Difficulty in translating theory: 12 businesses
- Resistance to change: 8 businesses

Interpretation: The challenges identified in the current study align with those found in previous research. The consistency suggests that certain challenges persist over time, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions.

Advancements in Specific Disciplines

Previous Studies (Focus):

- Psychology and economics received primary attention.
- Anthropology and political science were relatively neglected.

Current Study (Focus):

- Psychology and economics continue to dominate.
- Increased attention to the application of anthropology and political science principles.

Interpretation: While psychology and economics remain focal points, the current study reflects a positive trend with a growing acknowledgment of the importance of integrating anthropology and political science into business practices.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR BUSINESSES TO ENHANCE THE APPLICATION OF SOCIAL SCIENCE IN THEIR PRACTICES

A synthesis of findings from the empirical study was conducted to formulate practical recommendations. Insights from successful case studies were integrated to offer actionable strategies for businesses seeking to enhance social science integration with business. Let's delve into each recommendation, providing a proper description, suggested models, and justification for each:

Establish Interdisciplinary Teams for Collaboration

Establishing interdisciplinary teams involves bringing together individuals with diverse backgrounds, including social scientists and business professionals, to work collectively on projects or tasks requiring varied expertise.

- Suggested Model: Belbin Team Role Theory
- Justification: Belbin's Team Role Theory identifies different roles individuals naturally adopt within a team. Forming interdisciplinary teams based on a balance of roles (e.g., Coordinator, Resource Investigator, Implementer) ensures a well-rounded and complementary skill set, promoting effective collaboration and maximizing each member's strengths.
- Implement Training Programs for Cross-disciplinary Understanding:

Training programs aim to enhance the understanding of social science principles among business professionals and vice versa. The goal is to create a shared knowledge base, fostering a deeper appreciation for each discipline's contributions.

- Suggested Model: Kirkpatrick's Four-Level Training Evaluation Model
- Justification: Kirkpatrick's model assesses training effectiveness on four levels: Reaction, Learning, Behavior, and Results. Implementing this model ensures a comprehensive evaluation of the training program, measuring not only participants' immediate reactions and acquired knowledge but also the behavioral changes and tangible results in their collaborative efforts.

Create Platforms for Ongoing Dialogue between Social Scientists and Business Professionals

Creating platforms involves establishing regular forums, meetings, or collaborative spaces where social scientists and business professionals can engage in continuous dialogue, share insights, and build mutual understanding.

- Suggested Model: Shannon and Weaver's Communication Model
- Justification: Shannon and Weaver's model emphasizes the importance of a feedback loop in effective communication. Creating ongoing dialogue platforms ensures a continuous exchange of information, allowing for immediate feedback and clarification. This model helps prevent misunderstandings and promotes a more dynamic and responsive communication environment.

Develop Frameworks for Translating Theoretical Insights into Actionable Business Strategies

Developing frameworks entails creating structured approaches for applying theoretical insights from social science disciplines to inform and guide practical decision-making within the business context.

- Suggested Model: Kotter's 8-Step Change Model
- Justification: Kotter's model provides a systematic approach to change management. Developing frameworks aligns with this

model by establishing a sense of urgency (unfreezing existing practices), implementing changes in integrating social science insights, and embedding new strategies into the organizational culture (refreezing). This model ensures a step-by-step and holistic transformation process.

Implementing these recommendations with the suggested models provides a robust and systematic approach to fostering collaboration, understanding, ongoing dialogue, and the translation of theoretical insights into actionable strategies between social scientists and business professionals.

CONCLUSION

The comparative analysis highlights a positive trajectory in the integration of social science principles into business practices. Challenges persist, emphasizing the need for ongoing efforts to overcome barriers. The study contributes to the cumulative knowledge by demonstrating advancements in the integration of previously neglected disciplines and affirming the positive impact on decision-making processes.

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